

1 CALY-SWE value set: An integrated approach for a valuation study
2 based on an online-administered TTO and DCE survey

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5 *Authors:*

6 Kaspar Walter Meili (Corresponding author),
7 Department of Epidemiology and Global Health
8 Umeå university, Sweden
9 kaspar.meili@umu.se, kaspar.meili@yahoo.de
10 Orcid: 0000-0002-9889-4406

11 Brendan Mulhern,
12 Centre for Health Economics Research and Evaluation
13 University of Technology Sydney, Australia
14 Orcid: 0000-0003-3656-8063

15 Richard Ssegonja,
16 Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences
17 Uppsala University, Sweden
18 Department of Medical Sciences,
19 Respiratory, Allergy and Sleep medicine research unit,
20 Uppsala University, Sweden
21 Orcid: 0000-0002-5323-5626

22 Jan Hjelte,
23 Department of Social work
24 Umeå university, Sweden
25 Orcid: 0000-0002-5269-1961

26 Kerstin Edin
27 Department of Epidemiology and Global Health
28 Umeå university, Sweden

29 Fredrik Norström,
30 Department of Epidemiology and Global Health
31 Umeå university, Sweden
32 Orcid: 0000-0002-0457-2175

33 Inna Feldman,
34 Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences
35 Uppsala University, Sweden
36 Department of Epidemiology and Global Health

37 Umeå university, Sweden
38 Orcid: 0000-0003-3329-6066
39 Anna Månsdotter,
40 Department of Epidemiology and Global Health
41 Umeå university, Sweden
42 Lars Lindholm
43 Department of Epidemiology and Global Health
44 Umeå university, Sweden
45 Orcid: 0000-0002-1633-2179
46

48 **Abstract**

49

50 *Purpose:* To explore and develop methods to use TTO and DCE data collected in self-
51 administered online surveys to elicit a CALY-SWE value set.

52

53 *Methods:* Building on existing methodological knowledge around DCE and TTO studies,
54 we optimized the web survey in an integrated approach that consisted of a qualitative
55 face validity study, an iterative web survey development, including a three-stage roll-
56 out, a customized experimental design, and a sample size simulation. Based on the
57 inconsistencies of TTO answers per participant, we assessed TTO data quality by
58 calculating a score, and examined the effect of excluding TTO data according to this
59 score on the value set modelling.

60

61 *Results:* Participants in the quality study informed improvements in the survey's visual
62 design and phrasing. Based on the sample size simulation, we judged a sample size of
63 1,500 with a balance of six DCE and five TTO questions to be appropriate for the
64 valuation study. Changes made for the second stage, for example the introduction of a
65 *learning* state and of colour-coding, improved TTO data quality. Excluding TTO answers
66 per-participant based on the score led to an improved TTO data foundation for the
67 model by several metrics, such as no inconsistent coefficients and reduced standard
68 errors relative to the coefficient magnitude.

69

70 *Conclusion:* Developing value sets is feasible with online administered DCE and TTO
71 questions if the web survey is sufficiently optimized and coherent with the experimental
72 design. The severity of inconsistencies could be used to identify and exclude poor
73 quality TTO data to strengthen the value set modelling.

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77 **Plain English summary**

78 CALY-SWE is a new instrument for measuring quality of life broadly and for use in economic cost-
79 effectiveness evaluations of social welfare interventions. To be used as such, a value set is needed to
80 assign quality weights to the states of lives used in the economic evaluations. However, no
81 methodology exists yet for CALY-SWE to derive a value set, and existing similar valuation studies
82 from the health context use costly person-to-person interviews.

83 In this study, we aimed to find appropriate methods for deriving a CALY-SWE value set using an
84 online survey.

85 We developed an online web survey with discrete choice experiment (DCE) and time trade-off (TTO)
86 questions. We used previous methodological knowledge from similar studies, qualitative interviews,
87 a statistical simulation for the sample size, and we rolled-out the survey in three stages to be able to
88 implement further improvements. We also sought a way to identify and exclude participants who
89 contributed poorer quality TTO answers to improve the underlying data for the value set.

90 The resulting survey was optimized for online administration with a shorter survey length of six DCE
91 and five TTO questions, compensated by an increased sample size of 1,500. We developed a score
92 based on illogical TTO answers for identification and exclusion of poorer quality TTO data. This
93 design made it possible to perform the CALY-SWE valuation study.

94

95 *Keywords:* quality-adjusted life year, time trade-off, discrete choice experiment, capability approach,
96 online survey, economic evaluation

97

98 *Word count:* 4101= 4221 – 46 (f3) – 51 (f2) – 23 (f1)

99

100 Introduction

101 CALY-SWE (capability-adjusted life years Sweden) is a new measure for quality of life
102 purposed for use in economic evaluations with broad social consequences [1, 2]. CALY-
103 SWE conceptually relates to the quality-adjusted life year (QALY) concept developed
104 within health economics [1, 2], and a value set is needed to use the instrument in
105 economic cost-effectiveness evaluations [3]. Value sets consist of quality scores, or
106 weights, on the [0,1] scale for all *states* that the instrument describes. CALY-SWE
107 includes six attributes (health, social relations, financial situation and housing,
108 occupation, political and civil rights, and security) where each has three levels (Do not
109 agree, Partially agree, Agree completely) , equalling 729 possible states [2]. Zero
110 corresponds to a quality of life equivalent to death, and 1 to a quality of life sufficient
111 for a flourishing life [4].

112 Traditionally in health economics, standard gamble and time trade-off (TTO) questions
113 have been widely used for measuring health state values. More recently, discrete choice
114 experiment (DCE) questions have also been widely adopted in the development of value
115 sets [3].

116 Both TTO and DCE questions provide complementary information on preferences. In
117 DCE questions, participants ordinally compare two states with each other, providing
118 information on the relative strength of levels and attributes. Results are, however, only
119 anchored relative to each other and not on the absolute [0,1] scale. TTO questions
120 evaluate a single state by comparing time spent in the best state with time in an
121 impaired state. The time in the best state is then gradually changed until the participant
122 states that both situations are equivalent. The quality weight of the impaired state
123 equals the time spent in the impaired state divided by the time spent in the best state.
124 TTO questions thus yield direct information on the absolute anchoring of states on the
125 [0,1] scale but are cognitively challenging [5, 6]. Recently, hybrid models [7, 8] have been
126 developed that can jointly estimate value sets from DCE and TTO data, making it
127 possibly to integrate the complementary preference information of DCE and TTO.

128 EQ-5D is a widely used preference-based measure where country specific values are
129 derived using the EQ-VT protocol [9] for person-to-person interviews. The EQ-VT
130 protocol has been refined over time and provides routines for both DCE and TTO
131 questions, defines their experimental design, the interview procedures, and in parallel
132 provides software for conducting the interviews. The protocol also focuses on interview
133 training and data quality monitoring per interviewer to increase data quality; for
134 example, it defines a minimum time to spend on the introductory TTO question.
135 However, the EQ-VT is designed for person-to person interviews, and unsupervised self-
136 administered surveys are not intended. Person-to-person interviews increase the costs
137 and requirements for sampling and data collection considerably compared to
138 traditional self-administered surveys, thus decreasing the overall feasibility. This
139 especially applies in the context of COVID-19 restrictions, which happened to coincide
140 with the CALY-SWE valuation study.

141 On the other hand, some evidence suggests that face-to-face supervised administration
142 leads to better data quality compared to unsupervised online administration for TTO
143 questions [10]. Data quality issues related to the challenging TTO format may also be
144 exacerbated by using a commercial panel of participants together with online self-
145 administration.

146 For the CALY-SWE valuation study we decided to rely on an online panel and a self-
147 administrated survey with TTO and DCE questions, as we judged this to be the most
148 feasible way to time- and cost-effectively collect data representative of the Swedish
149 population. However, given the evidence on issues related to online self-administration,
150 we implemented and tested multiple elements to adapt the methods and increase their
151 validity.

152 **Aim**

153 Our aim was to explore and develop methods for eliciting a CALY-SWE value set, based
154 on online data collection via a web panel, and by leveraging methodological experience
155 accumulated from existing studies using both TTO and DCE.

156 To overcome the challenging nature of data quality in online surveys, especially for TTO
157 questions, we adopted an integrated approach across several areas, which translated
158 into the specific goals of:

159 1) Optimizing face validity, usability and quality of the web survey and TTO questions to
160 ease understanding and increase participant engagement, using an iterative approach
161 consisting of a qualitative study followed by the staged roll-out of the main survey

162 2) Developing an experimental design optimized for online data collection that is suited
163 for a shorter survey length to maintain participant engagement and to ensure cost-
164 efficient sampling

165 3) Performing a sample size calculation to determine a sufficient sample size sufficient
166 to exclude poorer quality TTO data or to use only TTO data for generating the final value
167 set

168 4) Investigating ways of assessing TTO data quality and then excluding lower quality TTO
169 data

170

171 Methods and survey development

172 Web survey development

173 We implemented the survey in HTML, CSS, JavaScript, PHP [11], twig [12], mariadb [13],
174 and sqlite [14], featuring a mobile-first responsive design. This framework enabled us to
175 customize the web survey to a larger degree than existing commercial solutions while
176 adhering to Swedish data privacy and safety regulations. After the qualitative face
177 validity survey, we rolled out the survey in three stages to iteratively analyse the
178 collected data and in parallel improve the survey, until we deemed the data quality to
179 be satisfactory (Fig 1).

180

181 **Fig 1** Conceptual flowchart of CALY-SWE valuation methods. ▭ symbolizes data
182 collections and □ general processes and analysis steps. Arrows represent the workflow.

183 To improve usability, we focused on conveying information visually instead of relying on
184 textual information. This included attribute levels of the states and the number of years
185 for TTO questions. For both the DCE and TTO questions we used the same basic visual
186 layout, where attribute levels were visualized by adjacent vertical bars. The bars were
187 filled according to the level of the three attribute levels, either empty, half, or full. Full
188 CALY-SWE statement phrasing, and instructions were obtainable via help buttons. For
189 TTO questions we additionally displayed a horizontal bar that was filled according to the
190 number of years in each state (See supplementary section on the web survey and
191 Supplementary Fig S1 – S4).

192 Qualitative face validity study

193 To assess the face validity of the web survey, we conducted a qualitative study among
194 16 participants recruited from two local non-profit associations in Umeå, with varied
195 age and gender. From September to December 2020, participants filled in the survey on
196 a tablet at the premises of Umeå university and were afterwards interviewed by two

197 qualitative researchers (Jan Hjelte and Kerstin Edin), based on a semi-structured
198 questionnaire.

199 **Experimental design and sample size simulation**

200 Our main consideration was to produce an experimental design with a relatively low
201 number of questions per participant to keep the survey length short. To still collect
202 enough data, we intended to compensate by increasing the number of participants.
203 Because we aimed for a hybrid model, we also wanted to find the best balance between
204 the number of TTO and DCE questions administered, and an adequate sample size for
205 generating the value set with a TTO-only model.

206 To that end, we generated different experimental designs for different configurations of
207 number of TTO and DCE questions. For each configuration, we chose the number of
208 TTO and DCE question so that the predicted time for survey completion would be
209 approximately 20 minutes, based on timing data from the qualitative study. Twenty
210 minutes was the maximum we considered workable for cost-effectively sampling from
211 the online panel, as costs per participant increase with increasing drop-out rates for
212 longer surveys. The configurations consisted of 11 and two, eight and three, six and
213 four, four and five, and three and six DCE and TTO questions, respectively, with each 50,
214 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 700, 1,000, 1,400, and 2,000 participants.

215 To develop a D-optimal design for DCE, we used the orthogonal design approach
216 presented in Street et al. [15]. We used this same design for all configurations and
217 randomly picked the DCE questions for a block. For TTO, we generated the different
218 designs specific to the number of TTO questions per configuration by using the *skpr* [16]
219 package in R with the D-optimality criteria.

220 Thereafter, we ran simulations with different numbers of participants for each
221 configuration, using a hybrid and a TTO-data-only model, both with a varying intercept
222 for the TTO linear model. We generated the data with the same varying intercept
223 specification, and parametrized it based on results from an earlier pilot study
224 (unpublished). We evaluated the performance of the simulation in terms of the mean
225 credible interval (CRI) width and the mean absolute error of the weight posteriors
226 compared to the generative model.

227 **Comparison stages 1 and 2**

228 Directly comparing data quality between stages was not possible due to low and differing
229 sample sizes in each stage. We therefore applied a bootstrap approach to examine the
230 effect of changes between the stages. We randomly sampled 500 DCE answers and 300
231 TTO answers 10,000 times with repetition for each stage, and performed a logit and an
232 ordinary least squares linear regression for the bootstrapped DCE and TTO answers per
233 stage with a main effects model. We then compared the distribution of the log likelihood,

234 the mean standard error of the coefficients, and the number of inconsistent coefficients
235 (level 2 greater than level 3) between stages.

236 **TTO data quality and exclusion**

237 The EQ-VT [9] focuses on interviewer training, and poor quality data (defined by criteria
238 such as whether or not the interviewer explained the example for long enough, or if the
239 TTO answer for the pit state was the lowest TTO answer within a margin [17]) may be
240 discarded. By design, self-administrated online surveys are unguided, making it
241 impossible to rely on the interviewer performance for quality assessment.

242 To address this challenge, we explored alternative methods for assessing the quality of
243 the TTO answers and the possibility of excluding them, such as mean time per question
244 and per iteration, time spent on the TTO information page, and proportion of iterations
245 where the full capability state was preferred. We also developed a score based on
246 inconsistent TTO answers that considers the severity of the inconsistencies, called the
247 *combined inconsistency severity (CIS) score*.

248 To be logically consistent, participants' answers should value states with levels higher
249 than those of lower levels for the same attribute. An *inconsistency* can occur for two TTO
250 answers from a participant for the two states in a *dominated* pair. A dominated pair
251 occurs if all attribute levels of one state are higher or equal while at least one level is
252 higher than in the other state. If the TTO answer for the first state is lower than or equal
253 to the second state, the two answers are not consistent with this relationship.

254 Formally, for any two states S_j, S_k from a participant's TTO block with answers w_j, w_k ,
255 and i indexing the attributes, we define a strict inconsistency as:

$$256 \quad \forall i: S_{ji} \geq S_{ki} \wedge \exists i: S_{ji} > S_{ki} \wedge w_j \leq w_k, j \neq k$$

257

258 Similarly, a weak inconsistency (can also occur if all levels are equal but weights are
259 different):

$$260 \quad \forall i: S_{ji} \geq S_{ki} \wedge \exists i: S_{ji} > S_{ki} \wedge w_j < w_k, j \neq k \text{ or } \forall i: S_{ji} = S_{ki} \wedge w_j \neq w_k, j \neq k$$

261 Weak inconsistencies were used for calculating the CIS score.

262

263 The *severity* of an inconsistency may be expressed as the absolute difference of the TTO
264 answers (W) and the absolute difference in TTO level attributes for the two involved
265 states (L), for participant p :

266

$$267 \quad L_{pjk} = \sum_i |S_{ji} - S_{ki}|$$

$$268 \quad W_{pjk} = |w_j - w_k|$$

269

270 For example, valuing 111111 (all six attributes on level 1, 'Do not agree') with 0.8 and
 271 333333 (all six attributes on level 3, 'Agree completely') with 0.2 could be considered a
 272 quite severe inconsistency, with the level differences being 12 (L) and the weight
 273 difference (W) equalling 0.6. On the other hand, an inconsistency involving 232323 and
 274 232333 with answers of 0.9 and 0.8 is less severe as there is only one level difference
 275 and a 0.1 weight difference. Such an inconsistency may occur due to the difficulty of the
 276 TTO question rather than a lack of engagement.

277

278 Across all values, we then normalized each score to [0,1] to make their scales
 279 comparable:

$$280 \quad Lnorm_{pjk} = \frac{L_{pjk} - \min(L_{pjk})}{\max(L_{pjk}) - \min(L_{pjk})}$$

281

$$282 \quad Wnorm_{pjk} = \frac{W_{pjk} - \min(W_{pjk})}{\max(W_{pjk}) - \min(W_{pjk})}$$

283

284 Afterwards, the score was summed for each participant p so that we could approximate
 285 data quality per participant and not merely exclude single unfitting answers:

286

$$287 \quad CISscore_p = \left(\sum_{jk} Lnorm_{pjk} + \sum_{jk} Wnorm_{pjk} \right)$$

288

289

290 The TTO experimental design did not contain the same number of support points for
 291 possible inconsistencies for each participant (ranging from 5 to 7), and different blocks
 292 may have been more challenging to answer consistently. We thus calculated score
 293 percentiles for each participant per block so that specific proportions of data could be
 294 excluded:

295

$$296 \quad CISpercentile_{score_p} = \frac{rank_{block}(score_p)}{n_{block}}$$

297

298 We assessed the impact of including only participants with better quality TTO data by
 299 comparing the results of an ordinary linear regression for including 30% to 100% of the
 300 data according to the CIS score, in 1% increments. We specifically looked at the weights
 301 for 333333 and 111111 and their difference that defines the value set's range, the
 302 adjusted R^2 , the number of inconsistent coefficients (where the coefficient for level 2 is
 303 larger than for level 3), the mean standard error and mean t-score of the coefficients

304 (coefficients divided by the standard error) and the coefficient with their 95%
305 confidence intervals.
306 We used R [18] for all data analyses with base R regression models, except for the sample
307 simulation using Bayesian hybrid models [8] that were estimated with stan [19] and the
308 cmdstan R interface [20].

309 Results

310 **Qualitative face validity study**

311 Participants' statements revealed that the DCE and TTO questions were challenging but
312 meaningful, partially engaging, and thought-provoking. Some stated that answering the
313 DCE block before the TTO block helped them to increase their familiarity with the
314 statement phrasing before tackling the more complex TTO questions. Most participants
315 were able to independently finish the survey by just relying on the on-screen
316 instructions.

317 During the qualitative interviews, we continuously developed the survey based on
318 participants' feedback. For example, we added an explanation video for the TTO
319 question, revised wording, and overhauled the DCE question layout to appear in the
320 same style as the TTO question layout. See Supplementary Table S3 for a detailed list of
321 changes and differences between survey versions.

322 **Experimental design sample size simulation**

323 We based the DCE design on an orthogonal array with six columns and 45 rows,
324 resulting in 43 pairwise comparisons after the removal of two dominated comparisons.
325 We used random blocking, where the DCE questions for each participant were
326 randomly picked from the 43 comparisons.

327 For TTO, we deemed eight blocks with three states per block to be adequate, and we
328 augmented each block with the pit state 111111 (all six attributes on level 1) so that
329 111111 would be evaluated by each participant, enabling estimation of 111111 with
330 greater precision. The DCE and TTO designs are provided in Supplementary Tables S1
331 and S2.

332 The sample size simulation resulted in a decrease of the mean 95% CRI and mean
333 absolute errors with increasing sample sizes. The hybrid model generally performed
334 better than the TTO-only model, especially for large proportions of TTO questions, but
335 differences were small both for mean CRI width and mean absolute errors for
336 configurations with at least four TTO questions. We decided on the configuration with
337 four TTO questions and six DCE questions, as we judged this to offer a good balance of
338 TTO and DCE questions. With this configuration, we found that at least 500 participants
339 would be necessary for using both TTO and DCE data and 1,000 participants for TTO-
340 only data. We decided to set the target sample size at 1,500 participants, to give us a

341 safety margin and to leave the option to only use TTO data for generating the value set
342 or to exclude poor quality data (Supplementary Fig S5).

343

344 **Comparison stage 1 and 2**

345 We collected data in three stages (Fig 1): Stage 1 targeted 100 participants and took
346 place from 22 November to 2 December 2021. Based on preliminary analysis after
347 stage 1, we aimed to further improve the TTO question format and piloted the changes
348 in Stage 2, targeting 200 participants (3 January to 12 January 2022). The main data
349 collection in Stage 3 targeted 1,500 participants (7 March until 18 April 2022).

350 In stage 2, we changed the iteration procedure, so that participants choosing “equal” in
351 the TTO question would not immediately proceed to the next question, but instead the
352 interval of reachable values would shrink around the current bisection point, and we
353 renamed the option to “about equal”. The goal was to reduce the incentive to finish the
354 question faster by choosing equal. We further decreased the TTO timeframe from 20
355 years to 10 years to reduce the expected number of necessary iterations.

356 To facilitate understanding and increase engagement, we changed the graphical layout;
357 instead of selecting radio buttons, clicking on buttons would now directly submit the
358 answer. We also introduced colour coding for the choices, where the first and second
359 choices were coloured in two distinct but neutral colours across DCE and TTO
360 questions, randomized per participant (Supplementary Fig S2 and S3). As a
361 demonstrated example, we also introduced a *learning* state as the first TTO state to
362 showcase the trade-off mechanism (details in Supplementary section on TTO learning
363 state), and removed one DCE question per block to compensate for the longer duration.
364 Other changes included participants being able to now navigate backwards.
365 Supplementary Table S3 depicts a detailed list of changes.

366

367 **Fig 2** Histograms of results of bootstrapped comparison between stages 1 and 2.
368 a) Logistic regression of DCE data with 500 draws with repetition.
369 b) Linear regression of TTO data with 300 draws with repetition.
370 10,000 bootstrap runs, main effects model. Discrete choice experiments (DCE). Time
371 trade-off (TTO). Standard error (SE).

372 The bootstrapped regressions from stage 2 compared to stage 1 indicated
373 improvements in TTO data quality in terms of lower mean standard deviation and
374 higher log likelihood with distinct distributions. The number of inconsistent coefficients
375 also decreased on average, but the distributions overlapped. In comparison, the DCE
376 distributions did not differ clearly between stages for all the indicators, and indicated on
377 average a decrease in data quality in stage 2 compared to stage 1. We deemed the data
378 quality satisfactory and launched stage 3 without any further substantial changes. The
379 final dataset included 199 stage 2 answers and 1,498 stage 3 answers but no stage 1
380 data because of the survey differences.

381 **TTO data quality and exclusion**

382 Among the assessed methods for TTO data quality assessment, we found the CIS score
383 (Fig 3) to perform better than the time per iteration or the proportion of times the full

384 capability was chosen (Supplementary Fig S6 and S7)

385

386 **Fig 3** Line plots of effects of including participants according to the CIS score percentile,
387 in 1% increments, in terms of the results of a linear regression main effects model.
388 Shaded error bands represent 95% confidence intervals. T-score (TS). Standard error
389 (SE). Combined inconsistency severity (CIS).

390 For higher percentages of included participants (100% corresponding to 1,694),
391 according to TTO CIS percentiles, the amount of variation explained by the model
392 decreased. This was indicated by a decrease in the adjusted R^2 , but also by a decrease
393 of the mean t scores and by a general decrease of the coefficients and the range of
394 333333 to 111111. Put differently, the model was less able to systematically pick up
395 inference patterns related to trade-offs between dimensions the more data were
396 included. Instead, the fitted values converged towards the mean of the TTO answers;
397 the intercept increased if more than 80% of data were included, together with a
398 decrease of the level-attribute coefficients. Beyond including 80%, the coefficient for

399 occupation level 3 became increasingly inconsistent, likely related to the general
400 decrease in coefficient magnitude. Interestingly, while in general the proportion of level
401 2 to level 3 coefficients remained constant, for occupation level 2 became larger than
402 level 3, and for finance & housing level 3 decreased compared to level 2 the more TTO
403 data were included.

404 Therefore, the results suggest using between 40% and 80% of TTO data for generating
405 the value set. Beyond 80%, the increase of the intercept would affect the value of
406 111111 and thus the lower anchoring of the value set on the [0,1] scale. In addition, the
407 effect of the attribute level coefficients increasingly loses strength beyond 80%. Model
408 performance of jointly estimated hybrid models with DCE data as well as
409 representativity considerations may also play a role when deciding the exact amount of
410 TTO data for generating the value set.

411 Discussion

412 We created an online-administered web survey for collecting TTO and DCE data for a
413 CALY-SWE value set, including an experimental design, and we estimated the necessary
414 sample size. We leveraged qualitative interviews and a two-stage survey roll-out to
415 improve the web survey, and developed a novel and sensitive way of excluding TTO
416 data with poorer quality This work paved the way for eliciting a CALY-SWE value set that
417 will be reported elsewhere.

418 Strengths include that we addressed the methodological challenges connected to online
419 administration with an integrated approach that resulted in multiple benefits: 1) the
420 qualitative face validity study allowed us to fine tune instructions and the appearance of
421 the web survey, and we were able to develop a web survey that focused on visually
422 conveying the task instead of textual information or oral guidance from an interviewer;
423 2) timing data from the qualitative study informed the sample size simulation, which in
424 turn facilitated an informed decision on the balance between the number of TTO and
425 DCE questions and the sample size, enabling cost-efficient online sampling due to
426 shorter survey length, that is compensated by an increased sample size to collect
427 sufficient data; 4) the staged roll-out allowed further improvement of the TTO data
428 quality in stage 2 as indicated by the results of the bootstrapped regression analysis;
429 and 5) We developed a per-participant score that reflected the severity of TTO
430 inconsistencies and enabled the exclusion of TTO data of an explicitly chosen
431 proportion of participants to partially offset limited data quality connected to online
432 self-administration. The CIS score also enable quality control for TTO data that is
433 independent of the administration mode as it does not depend on interviewer
434 performance.

435 Limitations include that we focused on a main effects only experimental design, thus
436 not considering interactions. For this valuation study, we focused on method
437 development and producing a readily interpretable value set. For generating the DCE
438 experimental designs we relied on orthogonal arrays as it was readily implementable

439 without relying on additional software, but it may be less efficient compared to
440 Bayesian experimental designs [21, 22].

441 Excluding TTO data based on inconsistencies is a contentious issue. In EQ-5D valuation
442 studies, sometimes evidently invalid answers, such as always responding with the same
443 value or the same pattern, or those selected in the feedback module, are excluded [23–
444 26]. Excluding TTO data based on inconsistencies via the CIS score indeed constitutes a
445 risk for data curation, where data are made to correspond to prior norms because
446 participants with larger uncertainties are discriminated against [27]. Similarly, concern
447 over consistency of preferences over the range of excluded data, while generally stable
448 in our study, still constitutes an important limitation as indicated by the changing order
449 of coefficients for levels 2 and 3 of occupation. On the other hand, under the
450 assumption that a portion of the participants did not engage in the task sufficiently to
451 correctly state their preferences, the score made it possible to transparently examine
452 the impact of excluding different amounts of data, on a continuous range. Hence an
453 informed, normative decision about how much data should be included could be made,
454 and the data quality itself is defined in relation to the total sample. In contrast,
455 excluding, for example, all participants that valued all states at 0.5 [9] is an absolute
456 either-or decision without granular control over how much data are excluded.

457 Compromised TTO data quality resulting from online administration, compared to face-
458 to-face data, or resulting from one interviewer per group compared to one interviewer
459 per person, previously been quantified in the form of increased standard deviations
460 [28], a lower number of trading iterations [10, 29], and a smaller range of the resulting
461 value sets [10]. Those results align with our findings: including poorer quality TTO data
462 according to the CIS score resulted in a lower range and a larger standard error of the
463 resulting weights. Similarly, changing the TTO iteration procedure in stage 2, so that
464 choosing ‘equal’ still required additional iterations to arrive at an answer, improved the
465 TTO data quality.

466 Other approaches to increase feasibility of valuation studies include videoconferencing,
467 which was found to be a viable alternative to face-to-face interviews for an Italian EQ-5D
468 5L valuation study [30]. Lipman similarly found that tele-TTO interviews were feasible
469 [31]. Compared to online self-administration, this still requires interviewers and training
470 to conduct the interview, imposing significant costs.

471 Further research into refinements of self-administered online valuation surveys may
472 additionally increase their feasibility. This particularly includes instructions and visual
473 design properties of TTO questions, and ways to assess data quality, but also relates to
474 general knowledge on the feasibility of online administration in combination with TTO
475 data quality assessment.

476 Conclusion

477 TTO and DCE data collected in self-administered online surveys may be used to elicit
478 value sets if the web survey development, the experimental design, and sample size

479 considerations are optimized and well-coordinated. The severity of inconsistencies can
480 be used on a per-participant basis to identify and exclude poor quality TTO data that
481 does not contribute to the modelling of preferences.
482

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602 Declarations and statements

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605 KWM: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology,
606 project administration, software, visualization, data curation, writing - original draft,
607 writing – review and editing.

608 BM: Conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing – review and editing

609 RS: Conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, writing – review and editing

610 JH: Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, writing –
611 review and editing

612 KE: Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing- review and
613 editing

614 FN: Supervision, writing – review and editing

615 IF: Funding acquisition, Supervision, writing – review and editing

616 AM: Funding acquisition, Supervision, writing – review and editing

617 LL: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, writing – review and editing

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